

ROLE OF PHYSICS EDUCATION FOR TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Physics is one of core science subject being offered in Nigerian schools and it forms the basis for the nation's technological advancement and human resource development. This paper discusses the contribution of Physics in the technological development as well as the job opportunities for Physicist and highlights some of the problems facing Physics education in our schools along with the recommendations.

Introduction. Physics is a branch of science that deals with energy and matter and their interactions. It is sometimes referred to as the science of measurement and its knowledge has contributed greatly to the production of instruments and devices of tremendous benefits to the human race. The study of Physics can leads to several scientific fields and professions such as engineering, manufacturing, mining and construction industries. Apart from this the knowledge of Physics plays a very significant role in the development of any nation.

Contribution of Physics to the Society . The importance of Physics cannot be over emphasized as it forms the basics for technological advancement of any nation. Physics plays a vital role in the development of any society in many ways, for examples; in electronics for developing transistors, diodes and integrated circuit(ICs) which

allowed the development of radio transmitters and receivers, televisions, radio tapes players and also modern machines for health services machines like X-rays were developed from the knowledge of Physics for used in taking images of the internal structure of patients and treatment of cancer and ultrasound to scan human body for diagnosis in hospitals and other health centers services. Solar energy is developed from the knowledge of Physics applied in the preservation, storage and utilization of sun light for preservation and processing of food and generating of electricity e.t.c. The knowledge of nuclear Physics plays a role in the preparation and processing of fuel for utilization of nuclear power, development of nuclear weapons e.t.c. In industries mechanics brings about new kind industries which depend on human skills and brains. Machinery also developed from mechanics helps in the

development of industries. Electricity and electronics developed from the knowledge of Physics is used for the development of telephones, optics cable, phonograph fibre and also internet that brings all parts of the world together. In transportation, cars, motorcycle, bicycle, ships, trains as well as aero planes are all development from the knowledge of Physics, this is because they all used electric motors and principles of moments in their various part. Computers and satellite were also developed from the Physics in taking and receiving messages from different part of the world. The contributions of Physics toward making the world worth living and boosting the prestige of several nations are too numerous to mention.

Job Opportunity for Physicists. A Physicist can work in the ministry of education and the ministry of science and technology as educator, educationist, scientific adviser and planner. Construction and engineering industries require the knowledge of Physicist for planning and developing enterprises. There is also opportunity in the aviation industry and military. Physicist can work in libraries and publishing houses as editor of scientific works and also Physicist can be valuable in research in ophthalmology and radiology therefore can find satisfaction in jobs in medical and health institutions. Physicist can be adopted in radar control at airports also as computer operator in the banks and Physicist can be fit as costumer service officer, production officer, senior technical staff, banking officer, marketing officer and programming officer to mention just a few in private sector (oil industry, banking, telecommunication and manufacturing industries) after sitting for aptitude test conducted by sector since the private sector

is not only concerned about the area of specialization of applicants bur also their quality.

Development in technology has been quite synonymous with advances in physics, and this has, over the years, influenced society beyond our wildest imagination. The indelible role of physics in society is thus wholly undeniable. Such influences and subsequent advancements could broadly be categorized as falling under two major categories - Macroscopic and Microscopic. The microscopic influence includes all phenomena related to atomic, molecular, and nuclear advancements. The macroscopic consists of everything within the ambit of laboratory testing, practical effects and advancements, and astronomical associations. As evident, these two categories are overlapping at times, and it is only through a close association between these two areas that the age of technology, as we know it today, has come to be.

How is Physics Related to Society and Technology? The first significant influence that physics exerted in terms of technological development led to the introduction of the steam engine, which subsequently ushered the age of industrialization. The steam engine worked on the laws of thermodynamics and greatly improved the efficiency of engines for starters. The applications of thermodynamics have subsequently also been used in later inventions like refrigerators, blowers, vehicles, etc. Here are some of the ways physics has left its impression on society through technological advancements.

Energy Industry . The contributions that physicists like Faraday, Tesla, and Edison had on the commercialization of electricity

is undoubtedly exceptional. They kick-started what is today called the age of globalization. The use of fossil fuels like petrol, diesel, coal changed everything from how the food was produced to how people travelled from one place to another. The influence was so prolific that it is difficult today to name an industry that wasn't influenced for the better, through these developments. With increasing awareness about the growing levels of pollution today, the world has shifted to alternative and renewable sources of energy. Even this gradual shift is being overwhelmingly influenced by physics. Dams, solar panels, wind farms, nuclear reactors - the energy of the future is overwhelmingly dominated and influenced by the physics of today.

IT Industry . The IT industry has been spearheaded by the extensive proliferation of computers in our daily lives, thus giving rise to the modern MNCs as we know them today. While the computer may not have been developed exclusively on the foundation of physics, the subsequent infrastructure, including the once ancillary but now vital data processing and network speeds, have been largely contributions of physics. For starters, John Bardeen was instrumental in the development of transistors and the theory of superconductivity, factors that led to the development of the early computer. The use of lasers was pioneered by C.H. Townes, which is now used from microsurgery to the most commonly used computer mouse. Even the use of optical fibres is based on the principle of total internal reflection of light. Optical fibres ensure better connectivity speeds and minimal data loss, thereby ensuring faster processing speeds and better reception of signals.

Medical Industry. In the medical industry, physics has been especially essential in radiology. W.K. Roentgen discovered X-rays, which is today the most popular, conclusive, and inexpensive method of determining fractures in the body. Ultrasonography works on the principle of reflection of ultrasonic waves and forms an essential part of both the medical as well as the defence industry. Another singular influence has been the use of nuclear medicine to cure diseases. Nuclear medicine today includes therapies that use radioactive elements to treat conditions like hyperthyroidism and certain types of lymphoma.

Communications Industry . In this case, by the communications industry, we refer both to the telecom and television industry, which has connected the world digitally, as well as the commercial vehicular industry like airlines which has made physical travel between places extremely easy. Telephones and televisions operate on the principle of electromagnetic waves. The generation of electromagnetic waves was first shown by the German physicist Heinrich Rudolf Hertz. Aeroplanes, on the other hand, at the fundamental level, operate on Bernoulli's principle.

Contributions that Went Beyond a Single Industry. There are various other discoveries that physics propagated that went on to change society in more ways than one. These include: Principle of levers and carriers – Archimedes; Galilean Telescope, Gaseous Thermometer - Galileo Galilei ; Geometric Optics - Johannes Kepler; Law of Elasticity - Robert Hooke; Expanding nature of the universe - Edwin Hubble.

Physics also helps us understand other disciplines like geology, agriculture, chemistry, biology, and environmental

science. Astrophysics and cosmology, the two branches of physics help in expanding our vision into the universe.

Conclusion. Thus, physics helps improve the quality of our life. Physics is necessary for the development of new gadgets. Most of the modern gadgets used in our homes make use of Physics to form and function. Understanding Physics makes us understand the world surrounding us. It also helps in the development of new

techniques for medical applications, such as computer tomography, magnetic resonance imaging, positron emission tomography, ultrasonic imaging, and laser surgery. This makes Physics touch all areas of our lives and illuminate them all. This brings to light the value of Physics in our life. Therefore, all educational institutes should and do promote the study of Physics and provide the necessary infrastructure for study and research in this field.

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